

A Study on the Effect of Unified Payment Interface (Upi) Among Youngsters - With Reference To Cochin Corporation, Kerala

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Abstract

The outbreak of Covid-19 has spotlighted the problem of direct cash payments. It supported the increased use of UPI system among the youngsters to avoid direct contact and focus on contactless payments which is supported by most of the banking institutions and our government to control our pandemic situation. The main objective of this study is to understand the effect of UPI on youngsters with special reference Cochin Corporation in Kerala. A wide range of applications like WhatsApp pay, Paytm, Google pay, Phone Pe etc. gained importance and recognition. Also, it reduced the problem of direct cash payment to a great extent. So, we consider this study as an opportunity to know how UPI affects the youngsters of our city. The majority of data is collected from primary sources; secondary data are also used for this study. Primary survey is conducted with 100 youngsters online as well as offline from Cochin Corporation. The selection of the respondents is based on the snowball sampling method.

Key words: UPI, Smartphone, P2P Transactions

Introduction

The episode of Corona virus pandemic appears to have made individuals center around contactless installments in their day to day routine. However a critical number of individuals began utilizing contactless installment choices like UPI (Brought together Installment Connection point) even before the pandemic, its use has gone up essentially post lockdown.. Nearly one-third of the total amount transacted on this four-year platform came in the last six months (the period following the lockdown). This market of digital payments highly effected by a smart tool known as smart phones, this has become a key component of people's personal, professional and financial online life. Smart phone culture made it very convenient to develop the use of various application/technology in our day to day life. Easy access to internet connection, one touch availability, secures financial transaction and it also influence the adaption of one touch payment. Therefore, to enhance the benefit of smart phone and digital technology and to evolve a platform for cashless payment and lucid financial transactions the Government of India developed a remarkable product, the "UPI" (Unified Payment Interface). UPI is a effortless payment tool developed by NPCI which is based on Immediate Payment Service

system. UPI can operate on a Smartphone and it works as an email ID for money. It makes possible Virtual Payment Address as a payment identifier for paying and receiving fund and works on single tap.

Rationale of the Study

The last decade has seen tremendous growth in the use of internet and mobile phones in India. In our nation UPI has been a pacesetter which is heading towards a computerised and a cashless economy. The growth of UPI was found rapid as it grown superior to digital wallets within a short span of time. According to the data released by the NCPI which operates UPI 5.04 billion transactions processed on the platform till now. This outstanding popularity of UPI prompted us to conduct a study in order to evaluate the effect of UPI especially on youth.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the effect of UPI on the youth with special reference to Cochin Corporation.
2. To investigate into the factors that contributes to the use of Unified Payment Interface.
3. To find out the reasons for choosing UPI transaction over cash transaction.
4. To study the level of awareness and usage of

Unified Payment Interface.

5. To find out the constraints faced by respondents by using UPI app.

Research Methodology

1. Research Design

The present study is descriptive, quantitative and empirical in nature. It is descriptive in the sense that it tries to identify various characteristics of research problem. It is quantitative because it involves numerical expression, and it is empirical since it examine, analyses and interprets collected data in order to arrive at conclusions.

Research Instrument: Questionnaire is the research instrument used here consisting of series of question and other prompts for the purpose of gathering information from respondents.

2. Type of Data Source

The study was conducted based on primary and secondary data.

Primary Data: The primary data was collected from 100 respondents from Ernakulam locality with the help of well drafted questionnaire.

Secondary Data: Secondary data are collected through reports, magazines, newspapers, journals, periodicals and internet publications.

3. Sample Design

1. Sampling Technique: This study uses the Snowball sampling method.
2. Sample Size: The sample size consists of 100 respondents, selected from the population of youngsters in Cochin Corporation.
3. Area of Study: The area of study is restricted to respondents in Cochin Corporation.

4. Hypothesis

The purpose of established research hypothesis is to find out the impacts of Unified Payment Interface Applications among the youth in Cochin Corporation.

Following variables were taken into consideration.

H0: The level of satisfaction of youth on UPI application is independent to the factors.

H1: The level of satisfaction of youth on UPI application is dependent to the factors.

4. Tools for Analysis

The collected data were analyzed with the help of statistical tools like percentages, Likert- scales and tables. Chi- Square Test is used to measure and interpret the gathered data.

Review of Literature

Bijin Philip (2019) has done a study on the impact of UPI on customer satisfaction. The same was focused to examine the customer perception with regard to unified payment interface and analyse the effect of UPI services on the level of satisfaction of the users. Findings revealed that the customer has a positive attitude towards unified payment interface services and functions and there is

positive relationship between education of the respondents and usage of UPI services. Educated person are more inclined to use the UPI services and they encourage more peoples in the adoption and usage of UPI services. *Shivani Maheswari (2019)*, in the research named UPI (Unified Payments Interface): The futuristic Payment Method identifies the structure of UPI and presents the income attributes of users on a monthly basis. From the study it is found that 105 million income till Nov 17, as reported by National Corporation of India (NPCI). It is concluded from the study that UPI payments not only creating peer to peer transactions but also peer to merchant transactions *Rahul Gochhwal (2017)* in his paper "Unified Payment Interface—An Advancement in Payment Systems" concluded that UPI has enabled mobile phone to be used as a primary payment device for making and accepting payments. UPI leverages high tele density in India to enable every bank account holder to make digital transactions using a mobile phone. India, which has a poor merchant payment acceptance infrastructure UPI, enables even the smallest merchant to start accepting digital payments without the need for any POS machine. *Dr. Virshree Tungare (2018)*, "A Study on Customer Insight towards UPI (Unified Payment Interface) - An Advancement of Mobile Payment System" states that cashless transaction has become important component after the demonetization. The researcher conducted a study in Indore about the UPI payments and related E-payments modes. The result of the research indicated that majority of the respondents agrees UPI transactions are easy to use and it offers several cash backs and coupons as rewards. The study concluded that it is enhanced with the help of smart phone.

Theoretical Framework Unified Payment Interface

Unified Payments Interface (UPI) is a system that powers multiple bank accounts into a single mobile application (of any participating bank), merging several banking features, seamless fund routing & merchant payments into one hood. It facilitates the P2P transactions that can be performed as per need and convenience. In order to transact fund, a UPI ID and security PIN are necessary. Real-time bank-to-bank payments can be made using a mobile number or virtual payment address (UPI ID).

Advantages of Upi

1. UPI facilitates real-time fund transfers via mobile gadgets 24*7*365
2. It gives access to multiple bank accounts through a single mobile application
3. It offers single-click two-factor authentication

- while also offering single-click payment.
4. The customer's digital address provides enhanced security because the users are not supposed to reveal attributes such as Card number, Account number, IFSC code, etc.
 5. This platform enables users to split bills with their peers.
 6. It is a highly recommended substitute to the complexities of CoD or physical cash withdrawals from ATMs.
 7. Utility payments, online bills and barcode scan and pays are possible via UPI.

Disadvantages of Unified Payment Interface

1. UPI is a deal for smaller fund transfers, when an amount is high then other modes of online transfer are preferable.
2. Concerning online scams people hesitate to install UPI application to their mobile phones.
3. According to NPCI guidelines users can transact only an amount of Rs. 100000 per day.
4. Since the UPI pin is a very small digit,(4 to 6 digit) it is not safe, hence due care should be given while making payments.
5. Strong internet connectivity is a must for proper functioning of UPI transactions.
6. UPI is a very fast and safe medium, but sometimes it takes a lot of time to send the payment after the bank's server down.

Applications with Upi Feature In India

1. Google Pay
2. Phone Pe
3. WhatsApp Pay
4. Mobikwik
5. Paytm

6. SBI pay
7. Fedmobile
8. AmazonPay

Peer-To-Peer Transactions

It can be also referred to as person-to-person transactions, P2P transactions, or P2P payments are electronic money transfers made from one person to another through an intermediary, typically referred to as a P2P payment application. P2P payments can be sent and received via mobile device or any home computer with access to the Internet, offering a convenient alternative to traditional payment methods. In the P2P payment system, every individual's account is connected to one or more customer bank accounts.

Smartphone

A Smartphone is a portable digital gadget that merges mobile phone and computing task into one single unit. They are differentiated from feature phones by their powerful hardware potential and substantial mobile operating structure, which facilitate broad software, internet and multimedia performances such as music, videos, cameras, gaming etc. alongside key phone features such as voice calls, text messaging etc. Smartphone usually hold a number of metal-oxide-semiconductor (MOS) integrated circuit (IC) chips, comprises various sensors that can be accelerated by pre-installed third-party software and support cellular communications.

Data Analysis

Particulars	No: of respondents	Percentage
A. distribution of respondents based on gender		
1. Female	86	86
2. Male	14	14
Total	100	100
B. Usage of UPI application		
1. Yes	84	84
2. No	16	16
Total	100	100
C. If no, what is the reason?		
1. Security concerns	10	62.5
2. Inaccessibility of internet	2	12.5
3. No smartphone	4	25
4. Others	0	0
Total	16	100

D. Intention of use in future (both users and non-users)		
1. Yes	95	95
2. No	5	5
Total	100	100
E. The factors affecting the usage of UPI app		
1. Cash back offers and point redemption	5	6
2. 24*7 availability & time saving	49	58
3. Free of cost	15	18.5
4. Secured transaction	0	0
5. Contactless payment	15	18
Total	84	100
F. most preferable UPI application		
1. GooglePay	53	63
2. PhonePe	20	23
3. AmazonPay	3	3.5
4. Paytm UPI	6	7
5. Whatsapp pay	2	2
Total	84	100
G. frequency of usage of UPI app in a week.		
1. Less than 5 times	42	50
2. 5-10 times	26	31
3. 10-20 times	4	4.8
4. More than 20 times	12	14.2
Total	84	100
F. Opinion of respondents regarding the increased usage of UPI during pandemic & lockdown.		
1. Strongly agree	55	65
2. Agree	0	0
3. Neutral	15	1
4. Disagree	14	17
5. Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	84	100
H. nature of transactions done by youth using UPI app		
1. Recharge	8	9.5
2. Bill payments	0	0
3. P2P transactions	20	23.8
4. All of the above	56	66.7
Total	84	100
I. Awareness about the security measures regarding UPI App		
1. yes	60	70
2. no	26	30
Total	84	100

J. Reason for choosing UPI Payment over cashpayment		
1. Offers and discount	6	7
2. Contactless payment	38	45
3. Low risk of theft	20	24
4. Track spends	20	24
Total	84	100
H. Constraints faced by respondents while using UPIApp		
1. Crashing of application	20	24
2. Non response by bank	46	55
3. Delayed payments	5	6
4. Transaction limit	13	15
Total	84	100

Satisfaction Level on the Following Factors Regarding Upi

NO. OF RESPONSES					
Particulars	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Not Satisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Safety	5 8	8	5	8	5
Security	6 0	8	6	5	5
Privacy	4 5	15	8	8	8
Speed	4 0	10	30	4	0
Accuracy	4 8	26	10	0	0

PERCENTAGE %					
Particulars	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Not satisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Safety	68	10	6	10	6
Security	71	10	7	6	6
Privacy	54	17	10	10	9
Speed	48	12	35	5	0
Accuracy	58	30	12	0	0

Testing Of Hypothesis

H0: The level of satisfaction of youth on UPI application is independent to the factors.

H1: The level of satisfaction of youth on UPI application is dependent to the factors. DEGREE OF FREEDOM = (r-1) (c-1) = (5-1) (5-1) = 16

Table value at 0.05 level of significance = 26.296

Calculated value = 81.89

Since, the calculated value is greater than the table value = 81.89 > 26.296

So, that ***we reject the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis.*** That means the level of

satisfaction on UPI application among youngsters is dependent on the various factors like safety, security, privacy etc.

H1	H0	The level of satisfaction of youth on UPI application is independent to the factors.	Rejected
	H1	The level of satisfaction of youth on UPI application is dependent to the factors.	Accepted

Findings

1. Majority of the respondents are female.
2. Majority of the respondents use UPI Application.
3. Majority of the non-users and users have the intention to use UPI Application in the future and security concern is the main reason for non-usage.
4. 24*7 Availability & Time saving is the main factor affecting the usage of UPI Application. Offers and promotions have increased the usage of UPI.
5. Google pay is preferred by most of the respondents and they're using it less than 5 times a week.
6. Most of the respondents are using UPI app
7. for recharge, bill payments and P2P transactions.
8. Around 65% of the respondents were strongly agreed that pandemic and lockdown has increased the wide usage of UPI Application.
9. Majority of the respondents, i.e. 70% of
10. the respondents have full awareness regarding terms the and conditions regarding UPI
11. payment system.
12. Most of them preferred UPI payment over cash payment by reason of tracking spends and contact less payment.
13. Majority of the respondents face the non-response by bank as the major constraint while using UPI Application.

Suggestions

1. The Unified Payment Interface should publicise that it is regulated by RBI and it is secured in a highly encrypted format.
2. The Unified Payment Interface should realise a strong network support from the side of partnering banks are also a necessity to resolve the issues of delayed and interrupted transactions.
3. The Unified Payment Interface (UPI) should make necessary measures in speedy reversal of unsuccessful transactions.
4. The Unified Payment Interface can even upgrade their limit of peer to peer transaction.

Conclusion

This study aims to find out the negative and positive aspects of Unified Payment Interface. This study has revealed that, there is a drastic increase in the usage of UPI after the pandemic and lockdown period because, with the help of UPI we can make contactless payments. On the basis of the study conducted, about 84% of the respondents are users of UPI. However, they are also facing with certain difficulties. For instance, non-response by bank, transaction limit and crashing of application etc. UPI should

work on these difficulties faced by the existing users in order to retain them, as well as to captivate new users. About 16% are the non-users of UPI and their main reason for not opting this service is due to security concerns and absence of smart phone. However, absence of smart phones and internet facility is no longer an issue since UPI have introduced "UPI123Pay" from March 8th 2022 which permits to perform UPI transactions via feature phones. However, the public is not aware about this facility of UPI. Therefore, UPI should promote their new feature and publicize how secured it is, under the guidelines of RBI which will enhance its acceptance among the public.

Refernces

Websites

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unified_Payments_Interface
2. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/u/unified-payment-interface-upi.asp>
3. <https://unifiedpayments.com/>
4. <https://www.thehindubusinessline.com>
5. www.researchgate.com
6. www.ncpi.org.in
7. www.irjet.net

Books

Vishal Verma. "Unified Payment Interface: UPI" Page no: 11-14 Jaspal Singh. "Digital Payments in India" Page no: 4-9 Aditya Kulkarnu : "Auth N Capture" Page no: 23-25